

HIGH INTEGRATION OF RESEARCH MONOGRAPHS IN THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable 3.3 NERD service and API

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E-mail address	: pierre.mounier@openedition.org
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DRAFT VERSION

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This short document is briefly explaining the performed tests on the NERD application.

I. Objectives

The objectives of this deliverable are:

- NERD service is running correctly on the platform servers,
- the API is appropriately used and annotations follow a minimum robustness for each application fields and the usage load

II. Results

As expected the NERD service is correctly running, the annotations are following a minimum robustness for each application fields.

A. Deployment

The NERD service has been successfully deployed on the infrastructure servers. The average uptime is 100% (see figures of the last 7 days), with an average response time around 150ms:

nerd (port - Checked every 5 mins)

Uptime: Last 7 Days

B. Tests

Following in the document are explained some tests performed to ensure the correct functioning of the API, and the annotations.

The development lifecycle around the NERD service will continuously test and bring improvement iteratively. These set of tests are a set of sample examples used to provide some explanation on the methodology:

C. Technical analysis

1. Contextual disambiguation (EN)

Vichy in a modern text is recognized as the city in the south of France:

Nestled in a bend in the **ALLIER RIVER**, **VICHY** is one of **FRANCE**'s most luxurious locations. The peak era of this **AUVERGNE SPA TOWN** saw visitors flocking there to drink its healing waters and **BATH** in its **THERMAL SPRINGS**. **VICHY** has kept its reputation as a health retreat, helped along by the reputation of the cosmetic brand named for the town. Tree-lined boulevards laid out in the **19TH CENTURY**, and **ART-DECO** buildings such as the Opéra de **VICHY** add to the town's nostalgic feel. Among **VICHY**'s turn-of-the-century mansions and riverside parks, there's a rich collection of **CONFECTIONERY** shops as well.

VICHY

Type: **LOCATION**

Normalized: **Vichy**

Domains: **Biology, Sociology**

conf: 0.5168035578591792

Vichy is a city in the Allier department of Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes in central France, in the historic province of Bourbonnais.

topic's main category	Vichy
Wikivoyage banner	Vichy banner.jpg
sister city	Wilhelmshaven
Dewey Decimal	2--44597
Classification	
coat of arms image	Blason fr Vichy.svg
Commons category	Vichy
INSEE municipality code	03310
country	France
image	Zone urbaine (VICHY,FR03).jpg
postal code	03200
located in time zone	UTC+01:00
located in the	Arrondissement of Vichy

Vichy in a text talking about the second world war, Vichy is recognized as the filo-german government:

The french resistance, in particular around **PARIS** is often referring with dispregiative adjectives to **VICHY**.

VICHY

Type: **LOCATION**

Normalized: **Vichy France**

Domains: **Administration, Military, Sociology**

conf: 0.5490475762715401

Vichy France is the common name of the **French State** (*État français*) headed by Marshal **Philippe Pétain** during **World War II**. It represents the unoccupied "Free Zone" (*zone libre*) in the southern part of metropolitan France, the four departments of **French Algeria**, the **French Protectorate of Morocco**, and the **French Protectorate of Tunisia**.

Commons category	Vichy government (1940-1944)
named after	Vichy
coordinate location	latitude: 46.166667, longitude: 3.4, precision: 0.00001
topic's main category	Vichy France

2. Contextual disambiguation (FR)

French text from a diary of the resistance during the second world war: in this case the city Vichy is again correctly disambiguated as the *Regime de Vichy*:

J'INDIQUE qu'à mon avis tout ce PROCÈS a été MAL CONDUIT - il fallait RENONCER à la prétention de faire un PROCÈS JURIDIQUE, ou son simulacre, et proclamer que devant des CRIMES inouis, une SITUATION toute NOUVELLE, la NATION prenait une DÉCISION POLITIQUE, IMMOLER les hommes de la HAUTE TRAHISON : "Jetons à l'EUROPE, en DÉFI, une tête de ROI", jetons aux combinards de VICHY et de WASHINGTON, en DÉFI, une tête de TRAITRE.

VICHY

Type: **LOCATION**

Normalized: **Régime de Vichy**

Domains: **Administration, Military, Sociology**

conf: 0.5240985304479111

Le nom de **régime de Vichy** désigne le **régime politique** dirigé par le **maréchal Philippe Pétain**, qui assure le gouvernement de la **France** au cours de la **Seconde Guerre mondiale**, du au durant l'**occupation du pays** par l'**Allemagne nazie**. Le régime est ainsi dénommé car le gouvernement siégeait à **Vichy**, situé en **zone libre**.

Commons category	Vichy government (1940-1944)
named after	Vichy
coordinate location	latitude: 46.166667, longitude: 3.4, precision: 0.00001
topic's main category	Vichy France
Embassy ID	/m/011495

French text talking about the city of Vichy:

Je suis alle a VICHY a visiter la VILLE et son beau batiments.

VICHY

Type: **LOCATION**

Normalized: **Vichy**

Domains: **Biology, Sociology**

conf: 0.1992054915569085

Vichy (prononcé) est une **commune française**, située dans le sud-est du **département de l'Allier**, rattachée à la **grande région Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes**. Ses habitants sont appelés les *Vichyssois*.

topic's main category	Vichy
Wikivoyage banner	Vichy banner.jpg
sister city	Wilhelmshaven
Dewey Decimal Classification	2--44597
coat of arms image	Blason fr Vichy.svg
Commons category	Vichy

3. PDF Processing:

This test ensures the PDF is correctly processed, the language correctly identified and the annotation correctly provided.

For this example the PDF is correctly identified.

The authors and affiliations are correctly recognized and not processed by the NERD, since they don't contain useful information from the point of view of the NERD.

Service to call:

```
{
  "onlyNER": false,
  "resultLanguages": [
    "de",
    "fr"
  ]
}
```

Select a pdf file: distant.supervision.pdf

WW1	Reuters_1
PubMed_1	Reuters_2
PubMed_2	French_1
HAL_1	German_1

page 1/9

The language is not specified in the input query, and the entities are correctly disambiguated against the English Wikipedia:

people/authorship	people/region/country
people/deceased_person/place_of_death	Fyodor Karamzov, Clearwater
people/person/nationality	Marianne Yvonne Heemskerk, Netherlands
people/person/place_of_birth	Wavell Wayne Hinds, Kingston
books/author/works_written	Ytton Sinclair, Lanny Bradie
business/company/founders	W.W.G. Vince McMahon
people/person/profession	Thomas Mellon, judge

Table 1: Ten relation instances extracted by our system that did not appear in [Freebase](#).

[2004](#). Our [algorithm](#) uses [Freebase](#) (Bollacker et al., 2008), a large [semantic](#) [database](#), to provide distant supervision for [relation extraction](#). Freebase contains 116 million instances of 7,300 [relations](#) between 9 million entities. The intuition of distant supervision is that any sentence that contains a pair of entities that participate in a known [Freebase](#) relation is likely to express that relation in some way. Since there may be many sentences containing a given entity pair, we can extract very large numbers of (potentially noisy) features that are combined in a [logistic regression](#) [classifier](#).

Thus whereas the supervised training paradigm uses a small labeled corpus of only 17,000 [relation](#) instances as [training data](#), our [algorithm](#) can use much larger amounts of data: more text, more relations, and more instances. We use 1.2 million [Wikipedia](#) articles and 1.8 million instances of 102 relations connecting 940,000 entities. In addition, combining [vast](#) numbers of features in a large classifier helps obviate problems with bad features.

Because our [algorithm](#) is supervised by a [database](#), rather than by labeled text, it does not suffer from the problems of [overfitting](#) and domain-dependence that plague supervised systems. Supervision by a [database](#) also means that, unlike in unsupervised approaches, the output of our [classifier](#) uses canonical names for relations.

Our paradigm offers a natural way of integrating data from multiple sentences to decide if a relation holds between two entities. Because our [algorithm](#) can use large amounts of unlabeled data, a pair of entities may occur multiple times in the test set. For each pair of entities, we aggregate the features from the many different sentences in which that pair appeared into a single [feature vector](#), allowing us to provide our [classifier](#) with more information, resulting in more accurate labels.

cal (word sequence) features in [relation extraction](#). While [syntactic](#) features are known to improve the performance of supervised [RE](#), at least using clean hand-labeled ACE data (Zhou et al., 2007; Zhou et al., 2005), we do not know whether [syntactic](#) features can improve the performance of unsupervised or distantly supervised [RE](#). Most previous research in [bootstrapping](#) or unsupervised [RE](#) has used only simple [lexical](#) features, thereby avoiding the computational expense of [parsing](#) (Brin, 1998; Agichtein and Gravano, 2000; Elzioni et al., 2005), and the few systems that have used unsupervised [RE](#) have not compared the performance of these two types of feature.

2 Previous work

Except for the unsupervised algorithms discussed above, previous supervised or [bootstrapping](#) approaches to [relation extraction](#) have typically relied on relatively small datasets, or on only a small number of distinct relations. Approaches based on [WordNet](#) have often only looked at the [hypernym](#) ([is-a](#)) or [meronym](#) (part-of) relation (Girju et al., 2003; Snow et al., 2005), while those based on the [ACE](#) program (Doddington et al., 2004) have been restricted in their evaluation to a small number of relation instances and [corpora](#) of less than a million words.

Many early algorithms for [relation extraction](#) used little or no [syntactic](#) information. For example, the DIPRE [algorithm](#) by [Brin](#) (1998) used string-based [regular expressions](#) in order to recognize relations such as *author-book*, while the SNOWBALL [algorithm](#) by Agichtein and Gravano (2000) learned similar [regular expression](#) patterns over words and [named entity](#) tags. Hearst (1992) used a small number of [regular expressions](#) over

DATABASE

Normalized: Database

Domains: Electronics, Computer_Science

conf: 0.4905

A database is an organized collection of data. It is the collection of schemas, tables, queries, reports, views, and other objects. The data are typically organized to model aspects of reality in a way that supports processes requiring information, such as modelling the availability of rooms in hotels in a way that supports finding a hotel with vacancies. A database management system (DBMS) is a computer software application that interacts with the user, other applications, and the database itself to capture and analyze data. A general-purpose DBMS is designed to allow the definition, creation, querying, update, and administration of databases. Well-known DBMSs include MySQL, PostgreSQL, MongoDB, MariaDB, Microsoft SQL Server, Oracle, Sybase, SAP HANA, MemSQL and IBM DB2. A database is not generally portable across different DBMSs, but different DBMS can interoperate by using standards such as SQL and ODBC or JDBC to allow a single application to work with more than one DBMS. Database management systems are often classified according to the database model that they support; the most popular database systems since the 1980s have all supported the relational model as represented by the SQL language. Sometimes a DBMS is loosely referred to as a "database".

subclass of	Base (group theory)
Commons category	Databases
has part	Data
topic's main category	Databases
NLX Auth ID	00865521
GND ID	4113276-2
Freebase ID	/m/02oc6
Stack Exchange tag	https://stackoverflow.com
image	/tags/database
Gran Enciclopèdia	Database.svg
Catalans ID	0221295

4. Annotation format

The format of the annotations is JSON and follow the documentation, see the following piece of response:

```
{
  "runtime": 188,
  "onlyNER": false,
  "nbest": false,
  "text": "Development and maintenance of leukemia can be partially attributed to alterations in (anti)-apoptotic gene expression. Genome-wide transcriptome analyses revealed that 89 apoptosis-associated genes were differentially expressed between patient acute myeloid leukemia (AML) CD34(+) cells and normal bone marrow (NBM) CD34(+) cells. Among these, transforming growth factor-β activated kinase 1 (TAK1) was strongly upregulated in AML CD34(+) cells. Genetic downmodulation or pharmacologic inhibition of TAK1 activity strongly impaired primary AML cell survival and cobblestone formation in stromal cocultures. TAK1 inhibition was mainly due to blockade of the nuclear factor κB (NF-κB) pathway, as TAK1 inhibition resulted in reduced levels of P-IκBα and p65 activity. Overexpression of a constitutive active variant of NF-κB
```

partially rescued TAK1-depleted cells from apoptosis. Importantly, NBM CD34(+) cells were less sensitive to TAK1 inhibition compared with AML CD34(+) cells. Knockdown of TAK1 also severely impaired leukemia development in vivo and prolonged overall survival in a humanized xenograft mouse model. In conclusion, our results indicate that TAK1 is frequently overexpressed in AML CD34(+) cells, and that TAK1 inhibition efficiently targets leukemic stem/progenitor cells in an NF- κ B-dependent manner. ",

```

"language": {
  "lang": "en",
  "conf": 0
},
"global_categories": [
  [...]truncated
  {
    "weight": 0.024712202256986684,
    "source": "wikipedia-en",
    "category": "Leukemia",
    "page_id": 20566458
  },
  {
    "weight": 0.007624430448200346,
    "source": "wikipedia-en",
    "category": "Book publishing companies based in New York",
    "page_id": 32846198
  }
],
"entities": [
  {
    "rawName": "leukemia",
    "offsetStart": 31,
    "offsetEnd": 39,
    "nerd_score": "0.4610935765835119",
    "nerd_selection_score": "0.6596664755324777",
    "wikipediaExternalRef": "18539",
    "wikidataId": "Q29496",
    "domains": [
      "Medicine",
      "Health"
    ]
  }
],
[...]truncated

```

D. Content analysis

In this section are enlisted samples of tests performed by HIRMEOS' partners, focusing on the content and the treatment of the document they are providing to the project.

Here a set of tests from the University of Gottingen (UGOE) partner.

1. PDF Processing

Process of the Lichtenberg catalog:

Chapter 1

Introduction

In order to achieve a better understanding of functional processes in nature, researchers have always aimed at gaining deeper insights into matter, particularly on microscopic length scales [1]. As a major probe, visible light has since been used for optical imaging. However, this often limits the information depth to the surface or surface-near regions of the specimen, due to the low penetration depth of visible light for most materials. Moreover, according to Abbe's law [2] the resolution of the visualized structure inside transparent objects is limited by the wavelength used for inspection, at least in conventional microscopes.

Because short wavelengths are able to resolve fine features and furthermore provide a higher penetration depth, the discovery of x-rays by W.C. Röntgen [3] was a cornerstone for research. As x-rays cover the wavelength range from 0.01 – 10 nm, information about the inner texture of comparatively thick and optically opaque media can be accessed at high resolution. Using the Beer-Lambert law [4], the penetration depth can be calculated for a predefined transmission, when the attenuation coefficient for the specific radiation energy/wavelength is known. This coefficient comprises of several interaction mechanisms of electromagnetic waves and matter, but is dominated by absorption of photons according to the photoeffect.

Apart from absorption, specimens can also impart a phase shift on the transmitted electromagnetic waves, meaning that the oscillation states (for given time and space) of two waves are shifted with respect to each other. Distinct from the absorption, this second type of contrast mechanism is used by a variety of imaging techniques such as phase contrast microscopy [5, 6], phase contrast tomography [7, 8] and holography [9] in in-line [10, 11, 12] and off-axis geometry [13]. To fully exploit this contrast, waves are required which exhibit a fixed phase correlation in view of the spatial and temporal propagation, denoted as coherence. Since only intensities (modulus square of the wave amplitude) can be measured by x-ray detectors, phases or relative phase-shifts, respectively, have to be made visible by interference and retrieved by iterative algorithms [14, 15].

^[1] Through the photoelectric effect, free electrons are generated by the x-rays in a semiconductor material

MICROSCOPIC

Normalized: Microscopic scale

Domains: Physics

conf. 0.5525164883319033

The microscopic scale (from , mikros, "small" and σκοπέω, skopéo "look") is the scale of objects and events smaller than those that can easily be seen by the naked eye, requiring a lens or microscope to see them clearly. In physics, the microscopic scale is sometimes considered the scale between the macroscopic and the quantum realm. Microscopic units and measurements are used to classify and describe very small objects. One common microscopic length scale unit is the Micrometer (µm) - one millionth of 1 meter.

Freebase ID /m/03qc7x

References W I I

2. Text processing

Test of a piece of text from the abstract of a public document from the Gottingen University library:

cloud.science-miner.com/nerd/

Suchen

disambiguate - text

```

{
  "text": "Modern x-ray sources and analysis techniques such as lens less imaging combined with phase retrieval algorithms allow for resolving structure sizes in the nanometer range. For this purpose optics have to be employed, ensuring small focal spot dimensions simultaneously with high photon densities. Furthermore, the wave front behind the optics is required to be smooth enabling for high resolution imaging. Combining all these properties, x-ray waveguides are well suited to perform this task, since the intensity distribution behind the guide is restricted in two dimensions serving as a secondary quasi point-source without wave-front aberrations, showing also a high divergence, suitable for resolving fine features. Importantly, the radiation provided by the waveguide reveals a high degree of coherence, required by many imaging techniques. The waveguide itself consists of an air-filled channel embedded in a solid matrix, typical materials are silicon, germanium or quartz. While the entrance area is nano-sized, the channel length is in the millimeter-range, this way posing challenges to fabricate high aspect ratio geometries. Since the functioning of x-ray waveguides is based on the total reflection at small incident angles, the surface roughness of the channel walls must be as low as possible to avoid scattering and hence loss of intensity. To fulfil these demanding conditions, a process scheme involving spin-coating, electron beam lithography, wet development, reactive ion etching and wafer bonding is optimized within this work. To gain deeper insights into the principle of wave guiding finite difference simulations are performed, also opening access for advanced design considerations such as gratings, tapered and curved channels, or beam splitters, enabling for constructing novel x-ray tools as for example time delay devices or interferometers. Waveguides in all geometries are tested at synchrotron sources, accomplishing new benchmarks in x-ray optical performance. Here, the x-ray beam leaving the channel, propagates out to a pixel array detector in the far-field region. From the recorded data the intensity distribution in the near-field directly behind the waveguide is reconstructed, revealing an outstanding agreement with the simulations and electron micrographs. Since the radiation field of the waveguide is well-characterized and also tunable to meet the requirements of both the measurement setup and the sample, they are suited of a broad field of applications in coherent x-ray imaging.",
  "shortText": "",
  "metaVector": [],
  "language": {
    "lang": "en"
  }
}

```

Submit

Annotations Response

Modern **X-RAY** sources and analysis techniques such as lens less imaging combined with phase retrieval algorithms allow for resolving structure sizes in the **NANOMETER** range. For this purpose **OPTICS** have to be employed, ensuring small focal spot dimensions simultaneously with high **PHOTON** densities. Furthermore, the wave front behind the **OPTICS** is required to be smooth enabling for high resolution imaging. Combining all these properties, **X-RAY** **WAVEGUIDES** are well suited to perform this task, since the intensity distribution behind the guide is restricted in two dimensions serving as a secondary quasi point-source without wave-front **ABERRATIONS**, showing also a high divergence, suitable for resolving fine features. Importantly, the **RADIATION** provided by the **WAVEGUIDE** reveals a high **DEGREE OF COHERENCE**, required by many imaging techniques. The **WAVEGUIDE** itself consists of an air-filled channel embedded in a solid **MATRIX**, typical materials are **SILICON**, **GERMANIUM** or **QUARTZ**. While the entrance area is nano-sized, the channel length is in the millimeter-range, this way posing challenges to fabricate high **ASPECT RATIO** geometries. Since the functioning of **X-RAY** **WAVEGUIDES** is based on the **TOTAL REFLECTION** at small incident **ANGLES**, the **ROUGHNESS** of the channel walls must be as low as possible to avoid **SCATTERING** and hence loss of intensity. To fulfil these demanding conditions, a process scheme involving **SPIN-COATING**, **ELECTRON BEAM LITHOGRAPHY**, wet development, **REACTIVE ION ETCHING** and **WAFER** bonding is optimized within this work. To gain deeper insights into the principle of wave guiding **FINITE DIFFERENCE** simulations are performed, also opening access for advanced design considerations such as gratings, tapered and curved channels, or **BEAM SPLITTERS** enabling for constructing novel **X-RAY** tools as for example time delay devices or interferometers. **WAVEGUIDES** in all geometries are tested at **SYNCHROTRON** sources, accomplishing new benchmarks in **X-RAY** optical performance. Here, the **X-RAY** beam leaving the channel, propagates out to a **PIXEL** array detector in the **FAR-FIELD REGION**. From the recorded data the intensity distribution in the **NEAR-FIELD** directly behind the **WAVEGUIDE** is reconstructed, revealing an outstanding agreement with the simulations and **ELECTRON MICROGRAPHS**. Since the **RADIATION** field of the **WAVEGUIDE** is well-characterized and also tunable to meet the requirements of both the measurement setup and the sample, they are suited of a broad field of applications in coherent **X-RAY IMAGING**.

FAR-FIELD REGION

Normalized: Near and far field
 Domains: Optics
 conf: 0.4901803780176996

The near field and far field are regions of the electromagnetic field around an object, such as a transmitting antenna, or the result of radiation scattering off an object. Non-radiative 'near-field' behaviours of electromagnetic fields dominate close to the antenna or scattering object, while electromagnetic radiation 'far-field' behaviours dominate at greater distances.

Freebase ID: /m/01n1jc

References:

Following the test of the output JSON format related to it:

III. Annex: Useful links

Source code: http://github.com/kermitt2/nerd_B

Licensing: <https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>

Documentation: <http://nerd.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>